

**PENGEMBANGAN AGROFORESTRI PADA LAHAN KRITIS DI
GAMPONG MEUNASAH MON KECAMATAN MESJID RAYA
KABUPATEN ACEH BESAR**

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ABSTRACT

The practice of agroforestry has actually been practiced by rural communities and even in some places. The implementation of agroforestry has an important role in the socio-cultural aspects of the local community so that traditional agricultural efforts carried out by converting forest land into agricultural land are the cause of frequent occurrence of critical land. Wise action is needed in rehabilitating critical land so that it can increase land productivity, it can also create sustainable land use and improve the quality and quantity of agricultural products, one of which is Agroforestry. The problem in this research is whether there is agroforestry development on critical land in Meunasah Mon Village, Mesjid Raya District, Aceh Besar Regency. The purpose of this study was to determine the development of agroforestry on critical land in Meunasah Mon Village, Mesjid Raya District, Aceh Besar District. This research was conducted on February 06 to March 04, 2021. The population in this study was all Meunasah Mon Village community with a total population of 388 families or 1,366 people. While the samples in this study were 50 respondents. The method used in this research is descriptive determination of the place of research and interviews (purposive sampling). Data collection techniques in this study are observation, interviews and questionnaires. Data processing uses simple statistical formulas and Likert scale calculations. Based on the results of the research data processing above, it can be concluded that from 50 respondents answered strongly agree 32%, answered agree 45.6%, answered disagree 16.2% and answered disagree 6.2%. So, it can be said that the development of agroforestry on the critical land of Gampong Meunasah Mon, Mesjid Raya District, Aceh Besar Regency is appropriate.

Keywords: *Angroforestri Development, Critical Land.*